

A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF E-COMMERCE LOGISTICS RESEARCH: GLOBAL TRENDS FROM 2020 TO 2025

Samet AYDIN

Doç. Dr., Maltepe Üniversitesi, sametaydin@maltepe.edu.tr, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2275-4682>

ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of e-commerce has significantly increased the strategic importance of logistics, particularly in areas such as last-mile delivery, cross-border operations and digital transformation. This study aims to map the intellectual structure and recent research trends in e-commerce logistics between 2020 and 2025 using bibliometric analysis. Data were retrieved from the Scopus database using the keywords “e-commerce logistics” and “ecommerce logistics,” resulting in 581 publications. The study employed VOSviewer software to conduct analyses focusing on keyword co-occurrence, country co-authorship, and source co-citation. The findings reveal seven main thematic clusters, highlighting dominant research themes such as optimization algorithms, last-mile logistics, sustainability, cross-border e-commerce, service quality, and smart logistics technologies, including artificial intelligence and blockchain. The country collaboration analysis indicates a geographically diverse research landscape with multiple regional clusters, while the source co-citation analysis identifies leading journals that form the intellectual foundations of the field, primarily in operations research and logistics management. Taken together, the results offer a structured overview of how e-commerce logistics research has evolved in recent years and highlight the key themes and publication outlets shaping the field. Unlike previous reviews, this study focuses exclusively on the post-2020 period using bibliometric mapping techniques, while being limited to publications indexed in the Scopus database.

Keywords: E-commerce logistics, Bibliometric analysis, Last-mile delivery, Optimization, Sustainability.

JEL Classification Codes: L81, L91, M11, O33.

E-TİCARET LOJİSTİĞİ ARAŞTIRMALARININ BİBLİYOMETRİK ANALİZİ: 2020'DEN 2025'E KÜRESEL TRENDLER

ÖZET

E-ticaretin hızlı büyümesi, özellikle son kilometre teslimatı, sınır ötesi operasyonlar ve dijital dönüşüm gibi alanlarda lojistiğin stratejik önemini önemli ölçüde artırmıştır. Bu çalışma, bibliyometrik analiz yöntemi kullanarak 2020 ile 2025 yılları arasında e-ticaret lojistiği alanındaki entelektüel yapıyı ve güncel araştırma eğilimlerini haritalamayı amaçlamaktadır. Veriler “e-commerce logistics” ve “ecommerce logistics” anahtar kelimeleri kullanılarak Scopus veri tabanından elde edilmiş ve toplam 581 yayına ulaşılmıştır. Çalışmada, anahtar kelime eş-zamanlılık, ülke ortak yazarlık ve birlikte atf analizleri yapmak için VOSviewer yazılımı kullanılmıştır. Bulgular, optimizasyon algoritmaları, son kilometre lojistiği, sürdürülebilirlik, sınır ötesi e-ticaret, hizmet kalitesi ve yapay zekâ ve blok zinciri gibi akıllı lojistik teknolojilerini içeren baskın araştırma temalarını öne çıkaran yedi ana tematik kümenin varlığını göstermektedir. Ülke iş birliği analizi, birden fazla bölgesel kümenin bulunduğu coğrafi olarak çeşitlilik gösteren bir araştırma ortamına işaret ederken, birlikte atf analizi, özellikle operasyon araştırmaları ve lojistik yönetimi alanında, alanın entelektüel temellerini oluşturan önde gelen dergileri ortaya koymaktadır. Tüm bu bulgular birlikte değerlendirildiğinde, e-ticaret lojistiği araştırmalarının son yıllarda nasıl evrildiğine dair yapılandırılmış bir genel bakış sunmakta ve alanı şekillendiren temel temaları ve yayın mecralarını vurgulamaktadır. Önceki incelemelerden farklı olarak, bu çalışma bibliyometrik haritalama teknikleri kullanarak yalnızca 2020 sonrası döneme odaklanmakta, ancak Scopus veri tabanında indekslenen yayınlarla sınırlı kalmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: E-ticaret lojistiği, Bibliyometrik analiz, Son kilometre teslimatı, Optimizasyon, Sürdürülebilirlik.

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1. Introduction

The rapid expansion of e-commerce has fundamentally transformed logistics and distribution systems globally. Increasing consumer expectations for fast, reliable, and flexible delivery have intensified the strategic importance of logistics in e-commerce environments, particularly in areas such as last-mile delivery, cross-border operations, and logistics network optimization (Hübner, Kuhn & Wollenburg, et al., 2016; Mangiaracina et al., 2015). Consequently, e-commerce logistics has become a critical research domain at the intersection of logistics management, transportation and information technology (Cano, Londoño-Pineda, & Rodas, 2022).

From 2020 onward, e-commerce logistics research has been shaped by a combination of global disruptions, rapid technological progress and increasing sustainability concerns (Andrei, Ioanid, & Scarlat, 2024). Researchers have increasingly focused on addressing complex operational challenges through data-driven and optimization-based approaches and exploring the role of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and the Internet of Things, in enhancing logistics performance (Chen et al., 2024; Dolgui, Ivanov, & Rozhkov, 2019; Wang, Han, & Beynon-Davies, 2019). Simultaneously, issues related to service quality, customer satisfaction, and environmental impact have gained prominence, reflecting the multifaceted nature of e-commerce logistics systems.

Despite the growing volume of academic research in this field, the literature remains fragmented across various thematic areas, methodological approaches, and geographical contexts. While numerous studies have addressed specific problems such as routing optimization, last-mile delivery, and cross-border logistics, a comprehensive overview that systematically maps the structure and recent evolution of e-commerce logistics research remains limited, particularly for the post-2020 period (Akil & Ungan, 2021; Giuffrida et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2021; Zennaro et al., 2022).

To address this gap, this study aims to provide a bibliometric analysis of research on e-commerce logistics published between 2020 and 2025. By analyzing publications indexed in the Scopus database using bibliometric mapping techniques, this study identifies dominant research themes, international collaboration patterns, and core academic journals shaping the field. Bibliometric methods and visualization tools, such as VOSviewer, are particularly suitable for this purpose because they enable the systematic mapping of large bodies of scientific literature (van Eck & Waltman, 2009, 2017). The findings offer a structured understanding of current research trends and support scholars and practitioners in navigating the increasingly complex landscape of e-commerce logistics research.

2. Methodology

This study employs a bibliometric research design to systematically map the intellectual structure and the recent research trends in e-commerce logistics. Bibliometric analysis is particularly suitable for identifying thematic patterns, collaboration structures, and influential publication sources within a research domain through the quantitative analysis of bibliographic data.

2.1. Data Collection

Bibliographic data were retrieved from the Scopus database, which is widely recognized for its comprehensive coverage of high-quality, peer-reviewed academic publications. The search was conducted using the following query:

“e-commerce logistics” OR “ecommerce logistics”

The search was applied to the title, ABSTRACT, and keyword fields. To capture recent developments and emerging trends, the time period was limited to 2020–2025. No additional filters regarding document type, subject area, or language were applied to ensure the broad coverage of the research field. As a result, a total of 581 documents were included in the final dataset.

2.2. Data Analysis

Bibliometric analysis was conducted using VOSviewer software, which is widely used for constructing and visualizing bibliometric networks. The analysis focused on three complementary techniques to provide a comprehensive overview of the research landscape.

Table 1 summarizes the bibliometric network characteristics.

Table 1: Summary of Bibliometric Analyses

Analysis Type	Items Analyzed	Clusters	Minimum Threshold	Key Finding
Keywords	40	7	5 occurrences	Optimization + sustainability lead
Countries	20	6	5 publications	China-EU-US regional clusters
Sources	9	5	10 citations	Operations research dominance

Source: Scopus query (2020-2025), VOSviewer.

First, a keyword co-occurrence analysis was performed using author keywords to identify dominant research themes and thematic clusters in e-commerce logistics research. A minimum occurrence threshold of five was applied, resulting in a network of 40 keywords grouped into seven thematic clusters.

Second, a country co-authorship analysis was conducted to examine the patterns of international collaboration. Countries with at least five publications were included, yielding a network of 20 countries organized into six collaboration clusters.

Third, a source co-citation analysis was performed to identify the core academic journals that form the intellectual foundations of the field. A minimum citation threshold of ten was applied, resulting in a network of nine interconnected sources, grouped into five clusters.

All analyses were conducted using full counting methods, and network visualizations were generated to support the interpretation of results.

3. Results

3.1 Keyword co-occurrence analysis

To identify the dominant research themes in e-commerce logistics, a keyword co-occurrence analysis was performed using author keywords. A minimum occurrence threshold of five was applied, resulting in a network of 40 keywords grouped into seven distinct clusters. These clusters reflect the main thematic concentrations and research directions in the field during the 2020–2025 period. The resulting keyword co-occurrence network, which illustrates the clustering of research themes based on keyword relationships, is presented in Figure 1.

As shown in Figure 1, the clusters are clearly differentiated, indicating distinct yet interrelated thematic areas within e-commerce logistics research.

Figure 1: Keyword Co-Occurrence Network of E-Commerce Logistics Research (2020–2025)

Source: Author's elaboration.

Cluster 1 primarily focuses on algorithmic and data-driven optimization approaches in logistics. Keywords such as big data, genetic algorithm, simulated annealing algorithm, TOPSIS, path optimization, and path planning indicate a strong emphasis on computational techniques aimed at improving logistics efficiency and decision-making processes in e-commerce environments.

Cluster 2 centers on optimization and analytics in cross-border and rural e-commerce contexts. The presence of cross-border e-commerce, machine learning, route optimization, rural e-commerce, and supply chain highlights research efforts addressing operational challenges and performance improvement in geographically dispersed and emerging markets.

Cluster 3 represents research on last-mile logistics from a strong sustainability perspective. Keywords such as last-mile, urban logistics, simulation, and sustainability suggest a growing focus on modeling urban delivery systems and assessing their environmental and operational impacts.

Cluster 4 emphasizes logistics network design and transportation optimization. The inclusion of e-commerce logistics, last-mile delivery, vehicle routing problem, multi-objective optimization, and transportation reflects studies aimed at balancing cost, efficiency, and service performance in e-commerce distribution systems.

Cluster 5 highlights service-oriented research in cross-border logistics. Keywords such as customer satisfaction and logistics service quality indicate increasing scholarly attention to service performance evaluation and customer-centric outcomes in international e-commerce logistics.

Cluster 6 captures the technological transformation of logistics systems. The keywords artificial intelligence, blockchain, IoT, and smart logistics reflect the integration of advanced digital technologies to enhance visibility, automation, and coordination in e-commerce logistics operations.

Cluster 7 focuses on rural logistics and service evaluations using advanced modeling techniques. The presence of bp neural network, rural e-commerce logistics, and service quality suggests niche but emerging research combining artificial intelligence methods with service performance analysis in rural contexts.

In summary, the keyword co-occurrence analysis revealed that recent e-commerce logistics research is characterized by a strong emphasis on optimization algorithms, last-mile delivery challenges, sustainability considerations, cross-border operations, service quality, and the adoption of smart logistics technologies.

3.2 Country co-authorship analysis

To examine the international collaboration patterns in e-commerce logistics research, a country co-authorship analysis was performed using VOSviewer. Countries with a minimum of five publications were included in the analysis, resulting in a network of 20 countries organized into six collaboration clusters. This analysis provides insights into the geographical distribution of research activity and the structure of international research partnerships in the field.

Figure 2 highlights the presence of multiple regional collaboration clusters, reflecting geographically structured research partnerships.

Figure 2: Country Co-Authorship Network in E-Commerce Logistics Research (2020–2025)

Source: Author's elaboration.

The results indicate a geographically diverse collaboration landscape. Cluster 1, consisting of Germany, India, Poland, Turkey, and Ukraine, reflects collaboration networks primarily involving European and emerging economy contexts, suggesting shared research interests in logistics optimization and regional e-commerce development. Cluster 2 includes Indonesia, Singapore, South Korea, Spain, and the United Kingdom, highlighting cross-regional collaboration between Asian and European countries with strong e-commerce infrastructures.

Cluster 3, comprising Brazil, France, Japan, and the United States, represents a group of countries with established research capacity and global influence in logistics and operations management research. These countries play a central role in shaping theoretical and methodological developments in e-commerce logistics. Cluster 4, which includes China, the Philippines, and Taiwan, reflects strong regional collaboration within East and Southeast Asia, a region characterized by rapid e-commerce growth and advanced digital logistics systems.

Clusters 5 and 6 consist of Hong Kong and Thailand, respectively, each forming an independent cluster. Although smaller in size, the inclusion of these countries suggests specialized or emerging contributions to the field, potentially driven by region-specific logistics challenges and market characteristics that warrant further investigation.

Collectively, the country co-authorship analysis demonstrates that e-commerce logistics research is internationally dispersed and supported by multiregional collaboration networks. The findings highlight the global relevance of e-commerce logistics challenges and underscore the importance of international cooperation in addressing complex logistics and supply chain issues.

3.3 Source co-citation analysis

To identify the intellectual foundations of e-commerce logistics research, a source co-citation analysis was conducted using VOSviewer. Sources with a minimum of ten citations were included in the analysis. Of the 383 sources identified in the dataset, nine met the citation threshold and formed the largest connected network, which was subsequently visualized and analyzed. These sources were grouped into five distinct clusters, reflecting the core academic journals underpinning research in this field. The source co-citation network, depicting the intellectual structure of the field through frequently co-cited journals, is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Source Co-Citation Network of Journals in E-Commerce Logistics Research (2020–2025)

Source: Author's elaboration.

Cluster 1 consists of Computers and Operations Research, European Journal of Operational Research, and Sustainability. This cluster represents the methodological and analytical foundation of e-commerce logistics research, emphasizing optimization models, quantitative decision-making techniques, and sustainability-oriented logistics solutions. As shown in Figure 3, journals related to operations research and sustainability are a central component of the co-citation network.

Cluster 2, which includes the International Journal of Physical Distribution and Logistics Management and the Journal of Business Management, reflects a managerial and strategic orientation. Research published in these journals focuses on logistics management practices, distribution strategies, and the integration of logistics within broader business and supply chain contexts.

Cluster 3 comprises the International Journal of Production Research and Transportation Research Part B: Methodological. This cluster underscores the importance of advanced modeling, transportation system analysis, and methodological rigor in addressing the complex logistics and routing problems associated with e-commerce operations.

Clusters 4 and 5 consist of Computers and Industrial Engineering and Transportation Science, respectively. Although these journals appear as single-item clusters, their inclusion indicates their specialized yet influential role in contributing analytical models, optimization techniques, and theoretical insights relevant to research on logistics in e-commerce.

Overall, the source co-citation analysis reveals that the intellectual structure of e-commerce logistics research is primarily grounded in operations research, transportation science and logistics management literature. The dominance of high-impact journals in these areas reflects the field's strong analytical orientation and its reliance on quantitative and optimization-based approaches to address emerging e-commerce logistics challenges.

4. Discussion

The findings of this bibliometric analysis provide a consolidated view of how research on e-commerce logistics has developed and diversified between 2020 and 2025. By jointly considering thematic patterns, collaboration structures, and intellectual foundations, this study offers insights into both the dominant orientations of the field and areas where research attention is expanding.

One prominent observation is the strong analytical and optimization-driven nature of recent e-commerce logistics research. The visibility of keywords related to algorithms, routing, network design, and multi-objective optimization suggests that scholars continue to prioritize operational efficiency and performance improvement in response to the increasing complexity of e-commerce logistics systems. The scale and time sensitivity of e-commerce distribution appear to have reinforced the relevance of quantitative models and computational approaches, particularly in areas such as delivery routing and logistics planning.

At the same time, the results indicate that sustainability and last-mile logistics have become central rather than peripheral research concerns. The frequent association of last-mile delivery with sustainability-related themes reflects the growing awareness of environmental impact, urban congestion, and energy consumption in e-commerce logistics operations. Rather than treating sustainability as a separate research stream, recent studies have increasingly integrated environmental considerations directly into logistics modeling and decision-making frameworks.

Another notable development is the increasing attention given to cross-border and rural e-commerce logistics. Research in these areas highlights the challenges related to coordination, infrastructure limitations, service quality, and customer satisfaction in geographically dispersed contexts. The emergence of these themes suggests that the field is moving beyond a primary focus on mature urban markets and is beginning to address the logistical realities of global and inclusive e-commerce growth.

Technological innovation also plays a visible role in shaping contemporary research agendas. The clustering of keywords related to artificial intelligence, blockchain, and the Internet of Things indicates sustained interest in smart logistics solutions aimed at improving transparency, automation, and system integration. These technologies do not appear as isolated topics but as enabling mechanisms that support optimization, sustainability, and service performance objectives across e-commerce logistics systems.

The country co-authorship analysis complements these thematic findings by revealing a geographically diverse research landscape supported by multiregional collaboration networks. The presence of both developed and emerging economies within collaboration clusters indicates that e-commerce logistics challenges are widely shared, whereas research responses remain sensitive to regional contexts. This pattern suggests opportunities for comparative and cross-contextual studies that can further enrich the field.

Finally, the source co-citation analysis confirms that the intellectual foundations of e-commerce logistics research remain firmly anchored in operations research, transportation science, and logistics management. While this analytical orientation has contributed to methodological rigor, it also highlights the potential space for future research to incorporate behavioral, strategic, and interdisciplinary perspectives that can complement existing quantitative approaches.

Taken together, these findings suggest that e-commerce logistics research is evolving toward a more technologically advanced, sustainability-oriented, and globally interconnected domain. The bibliometric patterns identified in this study not only clarify the current structure of the field but also provide a reference point for scholars seeking to position future research within the emerging and influential areas of e-commerce logistics.

5. Conclusion

This study provides a structured overview of recent research trends and intellectual foundations in the field of e-commerce logistics by employing a bibliometric analysis of publications indexed in the Scopus database between 2020 and 2025. By integrating keyword co-occurrence, country co-authorship, and source co-citation analyses, this study maps the thematic, geographical, and intellectual landscapes of e-commerce logistics research.

The findings indicate that contemporary research in e-commerce logistics is predominantly driven by optimization-oriented and data-intensive approaches, with particular emphasis on last-mile delivery, logistics network design and routing problems. Sustainability considerations and service quality have emerged as important research themes, reflecting the growing environmental and customer-centric challenges faced by e-commerce logistics systems. In addition, the increasing focus on cross-border and rural e-commerce logistics highlights the need to expand research beyond traditional urban and domestic contexts. The adoption of advanced digital technologies such as artificial

intelligence, blockchain, and the Internet of Things further underscores the ongoing technological transformation in this field.

Despite these contributions, this study has certain limitations. The analysis relied exclusively on the Scopus database and a specific set of search terms, which may have resulted in the exclusion of relevant publications indexed elsewhere or using alternative terminology. In addition, bibliometric analysis is inherently based on publication metadata and does not assess the methodological depth or the empirical quality of individual studies.

Future research could address these limitations by incorporating multiple bibliographic databases, expanding keyword strategies, and combining bibliometric techniques with systematic or qualitative literature reviews. Such approaches would allow for a more nuanced understanding of how theoretical, methodological, and contextual factors interact in e-commerce logistics research. Overall, this study provides a concise reference point for scholars seeking to navigate recent developments in the field and to identify promising directions for future investigation.

AI Use Statement

During the preparation of this manuscript, DeepL Write (AI-powered editing tool) was used to improve the readability and grammatical accuracy of the text. All AI-assisted edits were carefully reviewed and revised by the author, who takes full responsibility for the final content of the manuscript.

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